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A Creative Folio

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The Beautiful Mind of Lorenzo

As I browse my photo album, I remember Carol, my good friend, and the lines she often shared with me from her favorite quote, "There will always be a reason why you meet people. Either you need them to change your life, or you are the one who will change theirs." This quote from Angel Flonis Harefa holds as Carol shared with me how Lorenzo changed her and my life.

The bright blue sky of the day filled Carol's hands with sweat, not because of perspiration but nervousness as she approached her first class that day. We were told a few days ago that Carol's students would be just a few, which will be a blessing since Carol was a neophyte in the field. However, I know that is not her main concern; instead, it is the overflowing love and care she wanted to give all of them. Unfortunately, I overheard a colleague mention that Carol needs to be watchful of Lorenzo.

Teacher Carol, one of my closest friends in that school, was admired by everyone because of her genteel personality. In most of our conversations, she often recalled her experience with Lorenzo, a diagnosed attention deficit hyperactive disorder (ADHD) grade one student at a private school. Unlike other students, Lorenzo's parents are aware of his condition. When Lorenzo's father passed away, the heavy burden of raising Lorenzo was a sole responsibility accepted by her mother. Lorenzo was the firstborn of the Perez family and a bundle of joy, but when his parents found out about his condition, it was heartbreaking.

He was five years old when Lorenzo's father passed away, and at that time, her mom was pregnant with her baby sister. It was too much to bear, but his mom carried every challenge with total dependence on God's plan.

As Carol stepped into the façade of the school premises of her new home, she gazed with amazement at the ambiance, a feeling of warmth and relaxation far from the noise of the busy streets. The lush green garden near the classrooms created a refreshing scene, while the cold breeze caressed our tense muscles. In every step Carol took, she realized that tears began to fall; could it be because of the new beginning she would be facing as she shifted to a new

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career? Or could it be the new ambiance of the environment? Carol's mind was perplexed but delighted to be finally in her dream job.

After a few minutes, Carol finally arrived in her classroom. She smiled at the picturesque look of her room. It was just exactly the way she wanted it to be. The red floor mat, color-coded chairs, decors and posters, she personally chose them. Carol sighed in disbelief that each corner represents her love for her students. Then, just after a few minutes, each one of them arrived.

The day was filled with twenty-five students. Their parents still accompany some, while the others seemed relax and independent, but not for one student who looked different from the rest. Her mom immediately gave her telephone number and reminded me to call if there is a need. Her smile was gentle, but her look was fierce enough to signal that we must update each other often.

Carol began singing songs, arranging their things, classroom and school tour followed and when it was time for recess, Carol went around to see if they have snacks with them. Through their name tags, Carol finally found Lorenzo, seated alone while eating biscuits. At that time, Carol thought he was looking at her, but he was not. His eyes were cross-eyed. He kept on asking where Gilbert, his good friend, is. A boy in another group uttered, "he was in the restroom." Lorenzo breathed heavily, as if he found peace in knowing that Gilbert was just around the corner.

Carol stayed near Lorenzo for a while, then he asked permission to leave the room and went to the comfort room. After a few minutes, Carol was surprised when she saw Lorenzo with his wet hands; he never dried them, then he grabbed his chair and removed his shoes. Next, he stretched his hands, enough to reach the air from the ceiling fan, and he turned around while following the movements of the ceiling fan. Everyone was surprised and worried to see Lorenzo act that way. Then, Carol positioned herself near him since he might fall; he never fell, and Carol was thankful for that, but he never stopped. In fact, he seemed to be enjoying each turn of his hands and body.

While some of his classmates were anxious seeing him that way, Gilbert smiled and told him to get down because the teacher would get mad. Lorenzo followed and smiled back to her teacher. "He is really like that teacher, Gilbert said.

Pretending as if this was not a big issue, Teacher Carol just smiled back and held her thoughts. She sincerely told him, "Please be careful, next time".

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The day ended with smiles, more work to do, and more thoughts to ponder. As Carol sat on the chair, she narrated to me her worries about Lorenzo. I can sense the anxiousness in her face and the deep breath she made.

The next few days in Carol's class were filled with moments of discovery as she learned new things about her class and Lorenzo. At times, it moved her to tears since it was like a baptism of fire, but after a few minutes, she was moved to tears as she recalled the sweet moments with them.

Lorenzo began to show extraordinary mannerisms enough to frighten his classmates since he could not look his classmates in the eye. Lorenzo's command of the language is truly exceptional. He can assert himself in the class using English, and we are all amaze of that. This behavior, at times, can cause conflict that leads him to tears and tantrums. However, he never failed to amaze us with his clear memory; he can memorize the countries' capitals and flags, something only he can do. He often struggles with concentrating on tasks given. His only friend in class was Gilbert, and most of his classmates disliked him because he could not sustain conversations. Raising our voice never worked for him, so you need to tone down your voice whenever you are talking to him.

Understanding Lorenzo was not easy, and at times it frustrates Teacher Carol that she can only give a little to him, so I advised Carol to talk to his mom, and soon discovered many details about him. Carol adjusted her class routines and even my methodology of teaching. Instead of requiring him to sit for long hours, Teacher Carol gave him a task to lead the class and report attendance. Aside from that, Carol also asked him to make frequent rounds inside the classroom to give him the flexibility he needs while performing in class. Abut most of all, Carol instilled in his classmate's empathy and love.

There were times he was unmanageable, so they gave him the time he needed to be alone, but under her teacher's watch. After a few minutes, he would take the initiative to tell us that his mind is now clear and he is ready to join the class. Instead of swallowing in fear, we instilled in him love and support, not because he was special but because he was brilliant. His ideas are far beyond what we can think of.

There were several occasions that we saw his brilliant mind as he turned ordinary ideas into creative outputs. He is indeed thinking outside the box. Fueled by his curiosity, Lorenzo was able to suggest ideas that later on turned into real outputs. However, more than the brilliant mind, we say his heart, filled with compassion, love, and respect for everyone.

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When Carol celebrated her birthday, we were surprised with the birthday card he gave, "I love you teacher." A very simple phrase that made Carol and the rest of the class emotional.

As the school year ends, he frequently drops by her teacher's room to say hi. At times, we were surprised to see him seated in the last row, watching innocently. Then, Carol smiled back at him and approached him, "This was not your room, but you can see me later after your class." Lorenzo was like that until he finished sixth grade. His mom often thanks me for letting him be himself, and he would narrate stories where Lorenzo kept on singing the songs Teacher Carol taught him while saying his teacher's name.

Five years later, Lorenzo became my student, and this time I was more prepared to face him. He is more matured to carry out responsibilities because treatment was provided to him, together with therapy. He still has moments of confusion, but we both manage to surpass them because we know him very well.

Looking back at this experience, I must admit that Lorenzo taught us a very important lesson as a teacher, to instill love and respect for everyone, despite our inadequacies, because we all have a beautiful mind as one of God's creations.